

Digital Human Resource Management – A Theoretical Study

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Aishwarya, P. “Digital Human Resource Management – A Theoretical Study.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 90–94.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412500>

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Abstract

This research paper analyses the importance of digital transformation within public organisations and its impact on related human resource factors like human resource development, talent and performance management. Past research also indicates that the outcome of innovative HRM practices can be important towards retaining employees and their performance. At present, every business must seek to improve the quality of its workforce. To get the best human resource, an efficient and well planned strategy is required at the workplace. Therefore, technical advances are being made in the field of human resource with time and slowly the traditional HRM is being replaced by new and technically advanced HRM. Further, research articles, conceptual studies, review papers and other relevant content on the topic were accessed and reviewed through web sources and databases such as Proquest Database, EBSCO host and Google scholar to achieve the objective of the study. However, this study contributes to the existing literature by elaborating the role of innovative practices and technology in the context of competitive digital environment. Further, several implications were discussed for the purpose of promoting sustainable development of digital era. Study limitations and future research directions are also discussed. Digital HR, however, is more than just building apps. It encompasses developing a new mobile platform with a wide range of apps built with cloud and analytics technology behind the scenes. This platform can be used for hundreds of apps: from time and attendance to employee wellness, to recruitment, collaboration, goal-setting, and more. The design is integrated, the user experience is location-aware, and integrated data are used to inform and make recommendations to users throughout the day. To succeed in this new paradigm, HR teams will likely have to partner with IT, adopt design thinking, use integrated analytics, and analyze vendor solutions carefully. It represents a new world for HR technology and design teams, one that will open up new career opportunities and transform the impact HR has on the business.

Keywords: Innovation, HRM practices, Technology, Digital HRM, Design.

HRM and Digital HRM

In the present day, business is conducted on international scale and this involves the transfer of goods and services, technology, managerial knowledge and capital to other countries or across national boundaries. Globalization has made the world smaller through fast communication network. The economies of the world have become increasingly integrated (Bhagwati, 2004). Besides, we are now in a world where, digital HRM becomes a prominent

function of management compared to traditional HRM, because the survival of an organization depends on the quality of human resources available to it and/or use. Human resources department need to embrace the digital transformation and put good practices at the heart of their HR policy. However, there are number of challenges faced by human resource management around the world. In order to succeed in the modern world, it is necessary for business concerns to try expanding into the global market.

Digital Era

EBSCO and ProQuest databases are commonly used foreign language databases. Through the comparison of the EBSCO database and ProQuest database on the content and the retrieval system, it shows that EBSCO database includes much more key periodicals, various journals and full text journals which is keeping updating, and the full text journal inclusion has a longer time span. Moreover, the search functions and technologies are more powerful, which is better for precise retrieval and professional nature of databases. In regard to the use of databases, libraries could account their own costs, choose the platform with higher quality on the content and retrieval system and more comprehensive advantages.

Literature Review

HR professionals are already using technology to some extent, but the question of whether it is being accepted, maximized, and measured still needs to be answered. There is the imperative need to understand how HR can incorporate IT in their strategy to attract and retain the individuals who will create the competitive advantage and have the processes that support the business strategy (Huselid, 1995). Recent examples among local and companies overseas have shown the importance of IT being integrated into HR practices to increase profitability. For example, Deutsche Bank has made its human resources component a strategic partner in its business by making each human resources person a change agent and defining strategic competency. Development and information technology were prime movers in changing Deutsche Bank's personnel management (Svoboda & Schroder, 2001).

Previous studies have conceptualized "technology" as a useful instrument that may facilitate competitive advantage only when combined with existing firm capabilities (Tippins & Sohi, 2003). The conventional HRM practices such as recruitment, compensation, performance appraisal, retraining, redeployment, and rightsizing (Huselid 1995) are reported to be intentionally adapted with innovations, which are defined as innovative HRM practices to adopt skills, behaviors, and interactions during the process of organizational re-designing (Som, 2012). The major issue during implementation of HR practices was noted that, organizations do not invest much in to IT due to the prohibitive costs of doing so.

Previous researchers have shown that innovative HR practices have various benefits for the adopting organization (Agarwala 2003; Bhatnagar and Sandhu 2005; Bhatnagar 2007). In addition, it can enable rapid search, access and retrieval of information and can support collaboration and communication among organizational members (Wong, 2005). Agarwala (2003) found that among all the dimensions, introduction of innovative HR practices explained the maximum amount of variance in organizational commitment and thus were most effective in enhancing employee attachment to the organization.

Further, previous researchers have argued that the nature of relationship of the HR department in any organization with top and middle management, and the ways through which the HR strategy is linked with the organizational strategy (Ulrich 1997). Som (2007) proposed several factors that influence innovative HRM practice adoption in organizations operating in India i.e. national environment, or institutional framework, culture and incentive structures for innovative practices;

unionization; technological sophistication; organizational size, professionalization, restructuring; leadership and style of top management; and role of HR department.

Methodology

This study presents a thorough analysis of innovative practices in digital human resource management based on prior research studies. Digitalization and innovation HR practices have been reviewed and an in-depth analysis of literature related to study constructs has been conducted following the procedure of systematic review. An information search was made on databases with the purpose of accessing content related to study. The key words used for this search were, HRM practices, digital HRM, technology and innovative HR practices etc. The criteria for selecting studies were as follows:

- Articles and other study material were retrieved and sorted on the basis of well specified subject i.e. role of digitalization and technology on innovative HR practices.
- Study material chosen was ranging from 1981 to present.
- Empirical and theoretical studies conducted in the context of applying HR practices were preferred.
- For better understanding of the concept, studies having “digitalization”, “technology” and “HR practices” keywords in the title and/or abstract have been taken.
- A random bibliographic scan was performed on all the research studies to find out relevant study material.
- Articles were classified into two categories, i.e. literature emphasizing linkages between
 - a) Digitalization and HR practices,
 - b) Role of technology in transforming traditional HR in to innovative HR practices.

Study Findings and Discussion

Teece (2005) elicits that firms can achieve sustained competitive advantages by accumulating resources that produce economic value, are relatively scarce, and can sustain competitive attempts at imitation, acquisition, or substitution (Barney, 1991; Sampler, 1998). Many previous studies have relied on the assumption that adoption of IT would enhance performance (Dewettand Jones, 2001). The present study contributes to previous literature in several ways, particularly relating to the applications of technology dimension in implementing human resource practices. Study results were consistent with Jain, H., Mathew, M. & Bedi, A. (2012) who studied HRM innovations in the context of Indian and foreign MNCs operating in India. Previous empirical works have shown reasonably strong, positive relationships between the extent of a firm’s adoption of high-involvement HRM practices and organizational performance (Mac Duffie 1995; Delery and Doty 1996; Youndt, Snell, Dean and Lepak 1996). Study findings have important implications for organizations by way of inputting efforts towards HR system renewal. Prior researchers have also proven the linkages of innovative HR practices with higher commitment and involvement of employees by empirically testing the frameworks. The present study adds to academic knowledge by providing deep insights in to evidence pointing towards the significance of continuous renewal of HR practices through digitalization.

Conclusion

From the above literature review, it has been concluded that in today’s scenario there is need for transformation not only in terms of policies or structure but also the way it operates. Human resource management department has fundamental role for personnel recruiting, orientation and

performance appraisal, and compensation management and so on. Performance evaluation is one of the important matters for companies getting successful. Broadly speaking, today every firm need to include innovative HR practices which is extremely important especially in the process of attracting and rewarding employees which are two of the largest challenges they face. With the use of social media, virtual media has also become increasingly acceptable to organizations if it means that they can retain talent.

In this paper, digital HRM is essentially viewed as reborn concept for HRM. Gartner's IT glossary (2016) defines digitalization on a broad level and adopts a business transformation viewpoint "Digitalization is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and providenewrevenueandvalue-producingopportunities;itistheprocessofmovingtoadigitalbusiness". In the present scenario, human resource professionals started involving in renewing and redesigning the digitalized work practices and organizational structures. The digitalization has also enabled to organize tasks differently, as the information is no longer attached to the physical paper or location. So it has facilitated, organized the work and most importantly concentration which improves efficiency

Limitations and Future Research

Although this study demonstrates valuable insights of HR managers' perceptions of the challenges of digitalization, we believe it would be interesting to also interview HR professionals in other organizations operating in different contexts. As the case company of this study, Digital Solutions, was explicitly facing a digital transformation, it would be of value to compare our findings to the perceptions of HR managers operating in less 'digital' organizations, to explore to what extent their perceptions of the implications of digitalization correspond with our study. To evaluate findings from similar studies conducted in a broader spectrum of organizational contexts, would illustrate a more balanced perspective of HRM in a digital era. Lastly, in regards to our own reflection concerning that universities might have to update their curriculum of HRM studies, we recognize a need for future research to examine this further.

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